

Tracing the Distribution of Pink Spinel Anorthosites (PSA's) on the Moon

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Introduction: With the recent surge in exploration of the Moon, understanding the lithological diversity of the lunar surface is becoming increasingly important. In addition to constraining lunar geological evolution, lithologic distributions directly inform resource extraction strategies and the feasibility of a sustained human presence. Magnesium-rich spinel (MgAl_2O_4), for example, has been proposed as a potential energy source for rechargeable batteries via a spinel–rock salt phase transition capable of driving cathode reactions [1-2].

Data from the Moon Mineralogy Mapper (M^3) aboard Chandrayaan-1 revealed previously unrecognized lunar lithologies enriched in Mg-spinel (“pink spinel”) [3]. Among these, pink spinel anorthosites (PSA) are particularly notable, as they are dominated by Mg-spinel (>20%) and lack mafic minerals (>5%; [4-5]). Combined analyses of M^3 and Kaguya Multiband Imager data indicate that PSA materials are concentrated across the lunar highlands, select large impact basins [6] and in the South Pole–Aitken basin [7].

Constraining the mineralogical interpretation of these remote detections requires a robust understanding of spinel spectral properties. Controlled spectroscopic analyses of spinel reveal a broad absorption near $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$ and an absence of a $1 \mu\text{m}$ feature [8]. Although it is noted that with an $\text{Fe}\# > 6$, it can result in a $1 \mu\text{m}$ feature [9]. Maskelynite is spectrally featureless [10] and therefore does not modify the spectrum of the PSA lithologies.

A pink spinel-bearing troctolitic anorthosite (PSTA), NWA 12279, has also been investigated to better understand the spectroscopic characteristics of naturally forming pink spinel-bearing materials [11]; however, their spectra are largely dominated by associated mafic phases (olivine and pyroxene), complicating direct comparisons to orbital observations.

NWA 15500 is a dimict breccia composed of two distinct lithologies: a feldspathic fragmental breccia (Lith A) and a clast-poor troctolitic impact melt (Lith B). Lith A contains PSA clasts (up to $\sim 6.8 \text{ mm}$; [12]) that are modally dominated by spinel (36-59 %, $\text{Mg}\#$: 81-88) and low in mafics (0-9 % olivine), providing a unique opportunity to investigate the spectral signatures of a PSA without the influence of mafic minerals for the first time and to directly compare laboratory measurements with lunar remote-sensing data.

Methods: All samples were measured at the Open University using a JASCO MSV-5700 UV-Vis-NIR microspectrophotometer equipped with a $16\times$ Cassegrain objective and a $400 \mu\text{m}$ aperture, following established procedures [13]. A single chip of NWA 15500 containing an exposed PSA clast was measured in situ (Fig 1a), and a portion of the sample was subsequently powdered (Fig 1b). Bulk powders of Lith A and B were also measured. All spectra were collected relative to a Spectralon standard.

Results: The targeted area on the exposed PSA clast and homogenised powder reveals a broad $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$ feature and a lack of a $1 \mu\text{m}$

feature (Fig 2), indicative of a plagioclase + Mg-spinel lithology.

Fig 1: Optical images of the PSA chip (A) and powder (B) from NWA 15500. The circle represents the aperture (400 μm).

A minor feature at $\sim 0.54 \mu\text{m}$ is also present, most clearly observed in the powdered material, which is likely due to the tetrahedral Fe^{2+} spin-forbidden transition or an octahedral Cr^{3+} crystal field transition [8].

Discussion: The spectral properties of the PSA clast in NWA 15500 demonstrate clear similarities to previously observed spinel-rich sites across the lunar surface, especially Thomson and Theophilus (Fig 2) [5,7]. It has been previously suggested that at Thomson and Theophilus, Mg-spinel was exposed by these craters that impacted into the inner rings of Nectaris and SPA basins, respectively, likely indicative of a multi-stage excavation history for these materials, which is consistent with textural and crystallographic observations in NWA 15500 [12,14]. This data unambiguously links detections of Mg-spinel on the surface of the Moon with PSA clasts.

Fig 2: Mg spinel sites from [7; light pink field] Thomson and Theophilus from [5; black lines]. NWA 15500 PSA clast (solid pink lines – powder; dashed line – exposed clast).

Bulk measurements of NWA 15500's two lithologies and additional discussions on the implications of these results will be presented at the conference.

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